

WOMEN'S PREFERENCE OF TWO WHEELERS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY

A. Anandalakshmy* & Dr. K. Brindha**

* Assistant professor, Department of Commerce, VLB Janakiammal College of Arts and Science, Tamilnadu & Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, LRG Government College for Women, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, LRG Government College for Women Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: A. Anandalakshmy & Dr. K. Brindha, "Women's Preference of Two Wheelers with Special Reference to Coimbatore City", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 79-84, 2017.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2017 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The producers of Automobile products innovated a new thought of designing the two-wheelers in such a way to attract the women. Today most of the women prefer to travel through two-wheelers. A wide variety of two-wheelers of all category light-weighted, medium-weighted and heavy weighted vehicles have been introduced in the market. The objective of the study is to know the preference of ladies over two-wheelers and the various aspects, which determines the purchase or buying behavior and to know the expectations of ladies over two-wheelers. The sample size of the study was conducted in Coimbatore city with 150 respondents through convenient random sampling method. The tools and techniques used were simple percentage, chi-square and ANOVA. The obtained result of the study that majority of the women prefer scooty pep+ and most of the respondents prefer two wheelers due to smooth running and majority of the respondents have great impact on colour and model prefer the vehicle. New inventions and designs were introduced to meet the requirements of the current day affairs

Key Words: Preference of Ladies over Two Wheelers, Buying Behavior, Attitudes & Expectations

Introduction:

The Indian two-wheeler industry is experiencing a major shift in its shape and structure. The established players in the industry are taking a hard look at their portfolio of products and are in the process of reshuffling them to meet the expectations of customers. The last few years have brought about a great change in the consumer preferences for two-wheelers. The market leaders of yester years are being driven to maintain their leadership position in the forthcoming years. Those who have had a great going in the last few years are fighting hard to retain their new supremacy. The two-wheeler industry is perhaps the most happening place in terms of new models launched, upgraded products and innovative marketing techniques. Today the Indian two-wheeler markets in highly competitive the numerous players who offer anything and everything a consumer demands and that too at affordable price. The Indian two-wheeler industry is dominated by three players, Bajaj, Honda and TVS Suzuki, who account for 80 percent of the total two-wheeler market. The other players including Kinetic motors, LML and others account for the remaining 20 percent of the market. The industry can be divided in to three broad segments: scooters, motorcycles and mopeds. In the scooters segment Bajaj in the market leader, Honda is the market leader in the motor cycles segment and in the segment of mopeds, TVS controls the major chunk of the market. Most Indian players in the two-wheeler industry had been into some kind of strategic alliance, technical collaboration or joint venture with foreign players.

Statement of Problem:

Women play a significant role in the domestic and socio-economic life of the society. The prominent role of women in decision-making is due to increasing literacy, self-confidence, the control on independent income, and a more playing significant role in the family. The increase in urbanization, higher disposal incomes, falling interest rates, and poor public transport lead to increase in the volume of two-wheelers. An individual chooses personalized transport, instead of public transport to a desired location in most of the situations. This paper reports key findings from an interpretative study of women consumers' preference and buying behavior towards two-wheelers in Coimbatore City.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the preference of ladies over two-wheelers.
- ✓ To study the various aspects, which determines the purchase or buying behavior?
- ✓ To examine the expectations of ladies over two-wheelers.

Review of Literature:

M. Arutselvi (2011), in her research paper entitled on, "A study on customer satisfaction towards TVS Bikes" in kanchipuram town, has analyzed the performance of SARADAS Auto Agencies for retaining the customers by their authorized sales. The study has employed descriptive research approach and has adopted survey method for data collection. A sample of 130 respondents has been taken for the study. The study has

concluded that the sales of Saradas Auto Agencies for TVS two wheelers were good because of the right approach of a group of sincere mechanics.

Faiz Ahmed Shaikh (2011) A critical analysis of consumers buying behavior two wheelers (observations pertinent to Ahmed Nagar city, Maharashtra. The main objective of the study focus on identify the most preferred two wheeler manufacturing companies, In two wheeler marketing, relationship with consumers is very important and their cannot be good relationship unless we understand customer preference well. Information was collected from a sample size of 200 respondents. The toll used in the study is just below 80% of the total two wheelers market in India which is dominated by Hero Honda with a market share of 59%. Scooter segment market share is about 18% which is lead again by Honda motorcycle and scooter India Pvt. Ltd., with a market share of 43%.

Anuj (2011), Analyzing the state of competition in India two wheelers industry. The main theme of the study wills customer love to be with two- wheeler. The information on a foresaid factors will help manufacturer determine its manufacturing and marketing strategies for sustaining and growth of the business. The study had found that the automobile industry in India in one of the largest in the world and one of the fastest growing globally. Finally they conclude that report divides two wheelers industry in segments on the basics of price and scooters have been treated as separate segment.

Duggani Yuvaraju and Durga Rao (2014) have made a study on, “Customer Satisfaction towards Honda Two Wheelers: A Case Study in Tirupati”. The study has aimed to analyze the customer satisfaction of two wheelers. The study has found that 60 per cent of the respondents have come to know Honda Bikes through Advertisement media, 90 per cent of the respondents were completely satisfied with the mileage and performance of the bike, 73 per cent are satisfied with pick-up of the Honda Bike, 56 per cent of the respondents have attracted by the quality of the service. 50 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the design of the bike, 54 per cent of the respondents have considered the price of the Honda, 60 per cent of the respondents have felt the explanation were “excellent.” The study has concluded that there is a significant difference among the preferable factors such as, mileage, pickup, price and design.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the study reveals the preference of ladies over two wheelers. It confined with special reference to Coimbatore district. The vital purpose of the study has been conducted to identify the consumers evaluate their preferences and find out the factors in which it decides the buying decision, and to analyze the expectation level of two wheelers. The study creates a ground for future research in the similar field and would similar inferences that could be analyzed.

Sample Size: In this research work, sample size is 150

Sampling Area: The study was conducted in rural areas of Coimbatore District were only limited population was chosen on convenient random sampling

Methodology:

Both primary and secondary data were used for the present study. For collecting the first-hand information one hundred and fifty respondents were chosen by convenient random sampling method. Secondary data have been collected from Websites, Books and Journals.

Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ The study was restricted to 150 respondents in rural areas of Coimbatore District.
- ✓ The data was obtained through questionnaire and it has its own limitations.
- ✓ The result would be varying according to the individuals as well as time

Analytical Tools:

The following are the analytical tools applied for the analysis of the data collected:

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ Chi-Square test
- ✓ Analysis of Variance

Table: 1: Simple Percentage Analysis

Showing Personal Factor, Preference of Two-wheelers, expectations and Factor influencing to buy the Two-wheeler

Factor	Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age	<20 Years	20	13
	21-30 Years	50	33
	31-40 Years	63	42
	>41 Years	17	12
Marital status	Married	117	78
	Unmarried	33	22
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	6	4
	School level	39	26
	Under Graduate	90	60

	Post Graduate	15	10
Occupation	School student	9	6
	College student	30	20
	Working women	69	46
	housewife	42	28
Income per month	Below 10,000	57	38
	10,001-20,000	66	44
	20,000-30,000	15	10
	Above 30,000	12	8
Size of the Family	Up to two	18	12
	3-4	123	82
	Above 4	9	6
Preference of two-wheelers	Scooty pep	21	14
	Pleasure	9	6
	Scooty pep+	72	48
	Scooty streak	9	6
	Activa	30	20
	Others	9	6
Buying place of Two wheelers	Direct purchase	6	4
	Dealers	72	48
	Agencies from showrooms	57	38
	Others	15	10
Reasons for preferring the brand	Easy to handle	24	16
	Occupies less space	33	22
	Convenience	27	18
	Smooth running	66	44
Preference over physical appearance	Yes	141	94
	No	9	6
Source of information	Friends	69	46
	Relatives	45	30
	Media	24	16
	Newspaper	12	8
Criteria of colour of Two-wheelers	Yes	138	92
	No	12	8
Preference over starting procedure	Self-start	135	90
	Kick-start	15	10
Preference over mode of payment	Credit	105	70
	Cash	45	30
Period of using two wheelers	Less than 2 years	27	18
	2 to 4 years	108	72
	Above 4 years	15	10
Preference over price of the vehicle	High price	18	12
	Low price	3	2
	Not so high	39	26
	Economical	90	60
Preference over weight of the vehicle	Light weighted	15	10
	Medium weighted	126	84
	Heavy weighted	9	6
Cost of running and maintenance of the vehicle	High	15	10
	Medium	117	78
	Low	18	12
Factor influenced to buy the vehicle	Price	12	8
	Colour and Model	108	72
	Engine life	30	20

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The study reveals that majority of the women who own the two – wheelers belong to the category of income ranges from Rs. 10,001/- to 20,000 and with six of the choice given, majority of the women (i.e.) 48 % prefer scooty pep+. Majority of the respondents (i.e.) 94 % of them have preferred their vehicle considering the physical appearance because in a competitive market manufactures provide variety of models. Nearly 92 % of the respondents prefer their two – wheeler due to the colour aspect because a wide range of attractive colours are made available by the manufactures. Majority of them (i.e.) nearly 84 % of respondents prefer medium weighted vehicles. The study reveals that the cost of running and maintenance of the vehicle is medium for nearly 78 % of the respondents. With respect to price, 60 % of the respondents feel it as economical. Most of the respondents prefer self starter, because of its easiness. 70 % of the respondents prefer to acquire the vehicle on credit basis. The study reveals that nearly 44 % of the respondents prefer two wheelers due to smooth running. Most of the respondents have great impact on friends to prefer the vehicle. 72 % of the respondents have great impact on colour and model prefers the vehicle. The most of the respondent (i.e.) 48 % have bought their vehicle from the dealers. The majority of the respondents (i.e.) 72 % have been using the vehicle from 2 to 4 years.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Table 2: Chi-Square Test

Relationship between Income and preference of Two-wheelers

Factor	Calculated Value	Table Value	Degree of Freedom	Remark
Income	23.0201	24.996	15	Significance at 5% Level

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

It is observed that the table that the calculated value of chi – square is less than the table value. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is not significant relationship between income status and preference of two wheelers.

Table 3: ANOVA

Table showing Relationship between mode of payment and preference of Two-wheelers

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Means Square	F Ratio	5% F limit (or the Table value)
Columns	664	5	132.8	2.266	5.05
Rows	300	1	300	5.119	6.61
Residual	293	5	58.6		
Total	1257	11			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

It is observed above the table that the calculated value is less than the table value. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is not significant relationship between mode of payment and preference of two – wheelers.

Findings:

Based on the result majority of the women who own the two-wheelers belong to the category of income ranges from Rs.10, 001-20,000 and 48% of the women prefer scooty pep+. Most of the respondents prefer to acquire the vehicle on credit basis and 72% the respondents have great impact on colour and model prefer the

vehicle and with respect to price, 60% of the respondents feel it as economical and 84% of the respondents prefer medium weighted vehicles.

Suggestions:

It is found in the research that engine power is one of the main concerns of the customer. It is suggested to increase the engine power so as to increase the satisfaction of the customer. It is suggested to improve the mileage of the vehicle for increasing the satisfaction level of the users. It is suggested to reduce weight of the vehicle so as to give safety and make convenience to women customer. Suspension of the vehicle can be improved by providing shake absorbers at the front as well as rear. Normally the seats are made narrow at the front and rear and broader at the centre. The broader portion of the seats causes discomfort, so the centre portion of the seat can be slightly reduced in breadth. Most of the highways are in dilapidated condition. Potholes are seen everywhere. Hence in order to have a safe and comfortable journey shake absorber should be in a strong and fine condition. It is found in the research that facility for charging a cell phone in some vehicles can be provided to help the riders. It is suggested that the level of the ground clearance can be increased in mostly two wheelers.

Conclusion:

Customer's expectation and satisfaction are fulfilling by supplying them superior quality product at reasonable price. Customer preference to a large extent depends on the brand. Customers are annoyed of the mileage, resale value, easier to operate greater mobility, cheap spares and loan on installment facilities. Thus all the four companies, namely TVS motors limited, Honda motors company, Hero motors limited, Bajaj Auto Limited had technical collaboration with different Japanese auto giants, enjoyed good export potential, employed excellent quality control technique and overcome the tough time in the market by their innovative ability and efficiency. Keeping pace with the increasing demand two wheelers companies are factoring in the preferences and special needs of women while fine tuning their marketing strategies. All companies will duly satisfy the customer, by offering high quality products and services, which are new and traditional technologies as well as creativity and artistry and continue to be a known, trusted on love brand.

References:

1. Philip Kotler, marketing management, 11th edition prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi-2001.
2. R.S.N. Pillai & Bagavathi, modern marketing, S.Chand & Company Limited, New Delhi-2005.
3. C.R. Kothari, Research Methodology, K. K. Gupta for New Age International (p) Ltd, New Delhi.
4. S. P. Gupta, Statistical Methods, 2004, Sultan Chand & Sons publishing, New Delhi-2004. Sherleker S.A. -Modern Marketing Principles and Practices 2001.
5. Indian journal of marketing-Volume XXXVIII-Number: 3 March, 2008
6. Auto India-March & June 2006
7. Motor India-Feb & June 2006
8. The Hindu Survey of Indian industry, 2003
9. www.tvsmotor.com
10. www.hondamotor.com
11. www.herohonda.com